

A CHARTER FOR PUBLIC INTEREST INTERNET SEARCH

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Abstract

Digital web search systems are key infrastructures of the information society. They influence access to knowledge, public discourse and political participation. Yet their development is mostly driven by commercial interests and opaque decision-making. To address growing concerns about transparency, fairness and democratic control, the Open Search Foundation initiated a collaborative process to explore the ethical dimensions of web search. This article presents one result of this process – a Charter of ten guiding principles that aim to articulate normative reference points for a Public-Interest Web Search Infrastructure.

INTRODUCTION: WHY WEB SEARCH MATTERS FOR THE COMMON GOOD

Search engines and AI-based search applications are much more than technical platforms. As a critical infrastructure, they fundamentally shape what information becomes visible on the Internet, which perspectives enter public discourse, and how people make decisions. They influence access to education, democratic participation and the formation of public opinion.

At present, this central function is concentrated in the hands of a few global platform companies. Their interests are often opposed to the public good, democratic values and the roots of the Internet as an open platform. These systems, based on proprietary indices and opaque algorithms, prioritise commercial goals over the public interest. At the same time, the same few companies systematically collect sensitive user and behavioural data at scale. This concentration of power undermines transparency, pluralism and democratic control – and endangers fundamental rights such as privacy and freedom of information.

The common good is being neglected – an unacceptable situation from an ethical and societal point of view. Already back in 2000, Lucas D. Inrona and Helen Nissenbaum [5] argued that “web-search mechanisms are too important to be shaped by the marketplace alone” and that search engines “must work in the greater public interest.”

With increasing geopolitical tensions, the risks posed by this imbalance are growing. Political manipulation, disinformation, and government surveillance are becoming more likely, while smaller or alternative systems struggle to gain visibility. Legal and regulatory efforts have not yet succeeded in changing this structural imbalance.

Therefore, it seems necessary to establish a common set of rules that includes guidelines, recommendations and measures for an web search that is oriented towards the

common good, and as such not only serves society and puts people first, but also returns more control to society.

Background and Development

The Open Search Foundation (OSF), an independent non-profit organisation based in Germany, has initiated a multi-stakeholder process to develop an ethical framework for web search aligned with the common good. Supported by the Stiftung Mercator as part of the #EthicsInSearch project, this collaborative effort brought together experts from academia, civil society, and technology – most notably through the OSF’s Ethics Working Group and the project OpenWebSearch.eu that is building the prototype for an Open Web Index (OWI).

Starting with the question of what constitutes a public good web search, a series of workshops in different constellations explored its ethical and societal foundations. While various ethical frameworks for digital technologies already exist, a deliberately exploratory ‘blank page’ approach was adopted – seeking to identify relevant values, risks and mitigation strategies specific to the context of web search, rather than adapting existing models.

The process involved several steps: identifying and classifying values central to web search, mapping ethical risks, and developing concrete strategies to mitigate ethical and societal risks. The overall aim was to formulate guiding principles that define the normative, technical and institutional conditions for a search landscape that upholds individual rights, enables participation and strengthens both personal and collective autonomy.

Based on these findings, the OSF drafted a Charter for Web Search for the Common Good, the #FreeWebSearch Charter, which outlines ten guiding principles. In the following, the authors – both members of the OSF Ethics Working Group – briefly present these principles and their associated building blocks, and explain their specific relevance to web search in the public interest.

Defining ‘web search’ and ‘web search systems’

In this article we focus on web search related to the retrieval of different types of information (e.g. politics, news, history, science, art, etc.) from the Internet. As ‘web search’ no longer refers exclusively to classical search engines – it also includes AI-supported tools such as chatbots and generative models, platform-internal search functions, and hybrid systems that retrieve, rank and generate answers – this article uses the term ‘web search systems’ to encompass all those technologies that influence the visibility, accessibility and prioritisation of information in the digital sphere, whereas ‘web search’ means the whole societal and technological system in general.

THE TEN PRINCIPLES

Guarantee transparency and explainability

Transparency is essential for accountability, trust and participation. Without insight into how web search systems work, what data sources they use and what factors influence their results, it is impossible to identify bias, discrimination or undue influence. Transparency enables oversight, prevents abuse, and empowers users to make informed decisions and critically engage with digital processes. It is a prerequisite for digital sovereignty.

To support this principle in practice, four concrete dimensions of transparency have been identified:

Algorithmic and functional transparency: Research shows that the ranking of search results ‘has a dramatic impact on consumer attitudes, preferences and behaviour’, and in particular primacy effects influence the formation of attitudes and beliefs and can even have a significant impact on voting behaviour [1]. To counteract these effects, users need to understand how results are generated and what factors influence ranking and visibility. Key criteria such as ranking logic, moderation rules and personalisation mechanisms must be disclosed. Easy-to-understand explanations (e.g. ‘Why am I seeing this?’) and interfaces for user feedback and independent research are essential. Trade secrets should not be used to avoid scrutiny.

Transparency of sources and index data: Web search systems display only selected content. The criteria and processes used to include or exclude information must be transparent. Users and auditors need to understand which sources are included, how they are weighted, and where results and AI-generated answers come from.

Transparency of business models and influence: Vendors must disclose who controls the system, how it is funded, and how these structures may influence results. Advertising, political funding or other (financial) dependencies must be made visible. Paid content must be clearly identified.

Foster competition and technological independence

Without viable alternatives, dominant providers are likely to further cement their control over access to information – shaping public discourse, limiting choice and undermining transparency. ‘As any ranking per se prefers some items over others, the real problem comes when one search engine with a huge market share dominates what is shown in response to user queries.’ [6] Thus, a diverse search ecosystem is essential for competition, democratic participation and digital sovereignty. Users must be able to freely choose which search systems to use; this requires alternatives to dominant platforms, fair conditions for competition, and the development of independent infrastructures.

The realisation of this principle requires structural, regulatory and technical conditions, including the following core aspects:

Limit monopolies and organise the market fairly:

Effective regulation is needed to address market concentration and ensure fair competition. Governments must not only establish binding rules for data access, public accountability and plurality, but also secure rigorous enforcement.

Promoting open standards and interoperability:

Open standards encourage technological independence and innovation. This also applies to web search technologies, which consequently need to be open and interoperable. This includes open protocols and APIs, independent servers and shared infrastructure. The decoupling of indexing, ranking and user interfaces could contribute to technological sustainability and enable a more diverse and sustainable search ecosystem. [6]

Fostering alternative search technologies:

A pluralistic search ecosystem depends on visible and viable alternatives. However, public-interest, emerging or niche search systems face structural disadvantages in terms of visibility, funding, and infrastructure. Pluralism in search cannot be left to the market alone. Alternative public interest systems need long-term funding, visibility and support. Decentralised and open technologies need to be promoted through public and private investments in interoperable infrastructures, open indexes [6] and open source tools. Educational and public institutions should actively adopt and promote these alternatives.

Build sustainable and resilient infrastructures :

Technological sustainability is vital for long-term autonomy and public-interest orientation. A pluralistic search ecosystem requires deliberate, sustained support for alternatives that align commercial success with democratic values. This includes establishing viable economic foundations and shared technical resources that ensure long-term independence.

Strengthening the protection of privacy

Search behaviour reveals highly sensitive information about individuals – their thoughts, concerns, intentions and identities. If this data is collected, analysed or monetised without consent, it poses serious risks to privacy, autonomy and personal safety. The growing power imbalance between users and providers becomes especially problematic when behavioural data is used to personalise results, manipulate attention, or target users.

Protecting privacy in search is therefore not merely a technical or legal task – it is a matter of individual freedom, democratic integrity and public trust.

To implement this principle effectively, three areas of action are particularly relevant:

Privacy and data minimisation as a basic principle:

Digital search systems must respect the right to informational self-determination and apply data minimisation by default. This includes minimising data collection, applying privacy by design, anonymising behavioural data and treating user data as highly sensitive. Privacy settings must be set to maximum protection by default.

Returning data sovereignty to the users: Users must have full control over their data. This includes simple to use access, deletion and opt-out options, as well as protection against manipulative 'dark patterns'. Tools such as one-click anonymisation, data dashboards and complaint mechanisms are essential.

Ban on tracking, profiling and monitoring: Tracking and profiling must be prevented. This applies to all behavioural data, not just traditional identifiers. Profiling for advertising or political targeting must be prohibited. Non-profiling alternatives must be easily accessible. Aggregated, anonymous data can be used for evaluation and research, as suggested by Granitzer et. al. [3].

Giving users, content creators, and advertisers more control.

When Web Search Systems dominate the entire information ecosystem, they become gatekeepers that control all stakeholder relationships, unilaterally determining how information can be found, presented, or monetised. Empowering users, creators and advertisers restores balance, and creates a fairer digital marketplace where each stakeholder can align the search ecosystem with their legitimate needs and values.

Empowering stakeholder in web search systems involves the following three key elements:

Increase influence on the selection of sources, search processes and functions: Users should be able to influence the selection and weighting of sources. The way sources are prioritised shapes which perspectives users encounter. If this process remains opaque, critical engagement and informed assessment are hindered. Customisable filters, visualised metadata (e.g. origin, relevance, timeliness) and adjustable source preferences can help users navigate search more independently and pluralistically.

Facilitate control of search functions: Currently, providers determine all key parameters – from indexing and crawling to algorithmic sorting and display logic. Thus, users need influence over the search logic itself. Ranking settings, personalisation options, and content types should be adjustable. Interfaces must be transparent and allow non-personalised, ad-free or thematic search modes.

Improve control for content providers: Furthermore, content providers must be granted enhanced control, as current standards (e.g. robots.txt) are deemed inadequate [3]. Tools such as dashboards and machine-readable standards should facilitate fine-grained control over indexing, snippets and metadata.

Empowering advertisers and reduce platform dependencies : Advertisers depend on a few platforms for customer reach while platform corporations control both the marketplace and its rules. Advertisers must regain autonomy over their advertising strategies without being locked into monopolistic systems and non-ethical practices.

Preventing discrimination and enabling participation for all

Inclusive, non-discriminatory and accessible search is a prerequisite for education, participation and opinion formation in a democratic society. If search systems reinforce existing inequalities, they marginalise vulnerable groups and undermine digital justice. Thus, web search systems should connect people, not exclude them. They must be designed to ensure equal access to information – irrespective of factors such as background, language, disability, or social conditions.

Three main operational dimensions can be distinguished to address discrimination and foster inclusion:

Preventing discrimination through data and algorithms: The presence of biases in data and algorithms has the potential to perpetuate social inequalities; as such, it is imperative that systems are designed to detect and mitigate such effects, ensuring that no group is systematically marginalised.

Promoting fair treatment of content and content providers: Rankings must not favour commercial or dominant content at the expense of smaller, non-commercial or public-interest information. Providers must ensure equitable conditions and refrain from privileging (their own) content without transparency.

Ensuring universal accessibility and cultural diversity strengthens inclusion and equity. Search interfaces should follow accessibility standards (e.g. WCAG, EN 301 549) and support content in multiple languages, including regional dialects and minority languages. Without this, large parts of the population are denied access to digital knowledge.

Information plurality and diversity of perspectives

Democratic discourse, public knowledge and social cohesion depend on diverse viewpoints. If information is filtered in a way that marginalises certain views or reinforces dominant narratives, this distorts public debate, excludes minority groups and undermines equal access to knowledge.

In shaping which perspectives are visible, web search systems, including AI-powered applications, play a key role. They carry a special responsibility to reflect the complexity of public discourse and to actively counter one-sided representations.

Ensuring a diverse and pluralistic information environment involves the following fields of intervention:

Inclusion and promotion of a wide range of sources and viewpoints: web search rankings have a significant impact on consumer choices, mainly because users trust and choose higher-ranked results more than lower-ranked results [1]. Algorithms must not favour only dominant narratives or commercially strong sources. Rankings should not rely solely on popularity or technical relevance, but also reflect journalistic quality, pluralism

and social relevance. Smaller and independent sources must be included, especially on sensitive or controversial issues.

Prevention of algorithmic filter bubbles and echo chambers: While tailored results can increase short-term relevance, they risk creating echo chambers that limit exposure to alternative views. Providers must offer tools to manage or disable personalisation and ensure exposure to diverse viewpoints.

Equitable treatment of non-commercial content : Commercial dominance in search results creates an information landscape shaped by profit rather than the public good, while providers of non-commercial content often lack the financial capacity and knowledge to optimise their content for web search, resulting in their content becoming invisible. Equitable treatment of non-commercial content – from public health information to community resources – ensures that public interest is not subordinated to commercial interests.

Strengthening local and cultural content: Global platforms often prioritise dominant languages and centralised content, while regional or minority perspectives become invisible. To preserve cultural and linguistic diversity, regional and minority content should be supported through local weighting, multilingual support and targeted promotion.

Protect access to vital public information: Content of public interest, such as educational resources, health information and emergency services, is often vital and must be remain visible and easily accessible, rather than being crowded out by commercial search results. Providers should promote open access and work with trusted institutions to maintain quality and relevance.

Responsibility for environmental and social impact

Web search systems shape not only what we find, but also how societies evolve. Their development, however, often follows commercial or efficiency-driven logics that overlook broader societal and environmental impacts. As their influence grows, so does the need to align them with public-interest goals such as environmental and ethical responsibilities.

The social and ecological responsibility of search systems is reflected in the following areas of concern:

Technology impact assessments: Technology impact assessments should be mandatory to anticipate the risks of web search systems to democracy, public discourse and the environment. Trade-offs – such as speed versus energy consumption – must be critically assessed.

Minimising the environmental footprint: Search systems consume considerable energy and resources across their lifecycle. Search technologies need to minimise their environmental footprint. This includes efficient coding, durable hardware and transparency about resource use such as energy and water usage including transparent environmental metrics (e.g. CO₂ per search).

Public funding should support research on resource-efficient search.

Human rights and social responsibility: Providers of web search systems must uphold human rights throughout their supply chains, reject unethical industries and commit to inclusive, socially responsible development.

Industry-wide responsibility beyond legal minimums: A voluntary code of conduct can promote higher ethical standards, complement legal norms and serve as a benchmark for responsible practice. Independent assessments and transparency tools enhance credibility – a chance to gain market advantages especially for smaller providers.

Ensure and strengthen integrity and trustworthiness of search results

The reliability of search results is essential for informed decision-making, social cohesion and democratic discourse. The manipulation of search results on the other hand can distort public perception [4], mislead users and undermine trust in digital information.

Providers of web search systems must ensure that their systems are tamper-proof, unbiased and transparent in order to justify users' trust and safeguard the societal function of search. To safeguard the integrity of digital search, the following four aspects should be considered:

Protection against manipulation: Search providers need to protect against manipulation, such as bought rankings, politically biased autosuggestions or SEO spam. Clear rules, public safeguards and independent audits must be in place.

Protection against disinformation and harmful content: Disinformation and harmful content undermine trust and can threaten public health, safety and democracy. Providers must build in mechanisms to identify and flag misleading content and prioritise science-based, verifiable sources – especially on sensitive issues such as climate, health and elections.

Transparent and controllable autocomplete functions: Features such as Google's autocomplete that provide potential queries in the search box while a user is typing, not only 'frame how to consider particular ideas and their associated values', but also 'have the power to shape the terms of a user's enquiry, and consequently, direct wider public discourse' [2]. To reduce bias and manipulation, autocomplete mechanisms must be transparent, explainable, and under user control. Users should understand how suggestions are generated, be able to customise them, and have clear options to disable or report problematic entries.

Accurate presentation and interface design: The way search results are presented affects perception and decision-making. 'Current SERPs exhibit a very complex structure. They contain organic results, ads (search-based advertising; for example, text ads, shopping ads), verticals (e.g. news, images), direct answers and knowledge graph results'[8]. Interfaces must be clear, understandable, truthful and accurate. Search providers must not distort,

misrepresent or manipulate how information is displayed to users. Results must reproduce content correctly and not distort it.

Strengthen search competences and critical awareness

Confident and informed use of web search systems requires more than access – it requires competence. Yet studies show that this competence is often lacking. While users rate their search skills as high, they have limited understanding of how search engines work or are funded Schultheiß & Lewandowski [8]. Platz et al. [7] observe immaturity in user behaviour and low awareness of privacy risks among students. “Search literacy” and “search engine literacy” help users assess credibility, interpret results, and navigate complexity – supporting participation, protecting against manipulation, and enabling democratic engagement. Understanding the ethical and societal dimensions of search technologies also fosters ethical awareness and design.

This principle translates into three main fields of action, all addressing different actor groups:

Promote search skills specifically and at an early stage: Search skills need to be developed early and systematically. Curricula should integrate digital search skills from kindergarten to higher education. Tutorials and public resources can complement this in lifelong learning.

Anchoring ethical awareness in technology and companies: Those who design and operate web search systems also need to understand their impact. Ethics training, interdisciplinary exchange and clear guidelines will help ensure that technology serves the public good.

Foster critical research and public scrutiny : Independent research on Web Search Systems is essential for understanding their societal impact and ensuring accountability, yet independent researchers cannot adequately study them due to lack of data access, legal barriers, and insufficient funding.

Enforcing democratic control and binding rules

When the reach of web search systems becomes systemic, voluntary commitments are no longer sufficient. Without enforceable accountability, risks such as discrimination, disinformation, or abuse of power remain unchecked. Providers must be held accountable for how their systems affect individuals and society. Effective accountability requires binding rules, independent control, and societal participation from local levels through national regulation to international standards across national borders.

A rights-based and enforceable accountability framework requires attention to the following areas:

Mandatory obligations and independent oversight: Trust cannot be based on goodwill alone. Accountability requires binding commitments, independent oversight and introduce sanctions for harm. Without external oversight and real consequences, even well-intentioned ethics codes fail. Enforceable standards protect against abuse of power

and ensure providers are held responsible for the consequences of their actions. Users affected by biased or harmful results need clear avenues for redress.

Distributing power by participatory and democratic governance: Today, key decisions in the search landscape are made by a small number of commercial actors. Democratic governance can address this imbalance by distributing power and ensuring that oversight is independent, multidisciplinary and open to public debate. It can minimise one-sided influence, strengthen trust in digital infrastructures, and help incorporate different perspectives to align Web Search Systems with society's needs.

In this sense, a search infrastructure in the public interest should not only be accessible to the public – it must be shaped by the public.

International frameworks and shared standards: Free access to trustworthy information is a universal right – not a privilege of origin or market position. Search technologies are global, but rights and protection structures often end at national borders. Without international cooperation, powerful actors will remain highly influential, while local alternatives have little chance. Users in vulnerable regions are particularly at risk – from censorship, surveillance or exclusion from access to reliable information.

International cooperation and coordinated frameworks that work across borders are needed to reduce digital dependencies and enforce equitable standards worldwide, regardless of geography or market power. Human rights, transparency and public interest principles should be embedded in multilateral agreements.

CONCLUSION: ETHICAL ORIENTATION FOR THE FUTURE OF WEB SEARCH

The societal significance of web search has grown steadily over the past decades. As a central interface for access to knowledge, education, and public discourse, it shapes not only what individuals find, but also what perspectives are made visible, and how collective decisions are informed. Despite this relevance, the development and governance of web search systems has largely remained in the hands of private actors – driven by commercial incentives, technological optimisation and opaque decision-making structures.

This article outlined ten guiding principles for a public-interest-oriented web search as formulated in the #FreeWebSearch Charter¹. They are the outcome of an exploratory and interdisciplinary process initiated by the Open Search Foundation, building on the work of its Ethics Working Group. The principles are not yet a comprehensive ethical framework, but they aim to provide orientation for the further ethical, regulatory and institutional discussion and development of web search systems.

¹The #FreeWebSearch Charter was made public at the end of September 2025. <https://charter.freewebsearch.org>

While the challenges addressed in the Charter affect society as a whole, the responsibility to act lies particularly with those in positions of influence: policymakers, public institutions, search system providers, researchers, educators, civil society organisations and the media. As web search increasingly functions as a societal infrastructure, responsibility must be shared across sectors and national borders.

The principles also serve as a reference point for ongoing practical work – for example, within the European OpenWebSearch.eu project, where selected aspects are being explored and implemented.

Further development of a comprehensive framework for ethical web search remains an open and ongoing process. As a living system, it depends on the critical reflection, uptake and discussion by various stakeholders. The Charter, as a first step, aims to stimulate this debate and to provide a foundation for more in-depth analyses, mitigation and implementation strategies and concrete guidelines in the future.

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